

As an NIH-funded researcher, I want to USE OSF to share my data, so that I can comply with my data management and sharing plan and the conditions of my grant.

This use case highlights ways research teams can leverage generalist repositories to share project data.

Dataset Title:

Data for: Effect of Preregistration on Reproducibility

Investigators and affiliations:

Brian Nosek
Center for Open Science & University of Virginia

Eric Olson
George Mason University

Date:

01/01/2023

Data type:

Survey results

Use Case Date:

01/01/2023

Use case Contact:

blaine@cos.io

Background:

OSF is free to use by research producers and consumers. Research producers have fine control on privacy and security enabling them to keep some components of projects private and make other components publicly accessible. Research producers have control of data release and facility to manage data curation both before and after making data available. Versioning of files supports effective curation and historical preservation of content.

OSF individual projects, components, registrations, and preprints include metadata about their own licensing, include the text of the license in the interface and the API, and offer an option to write a custom license to meet content needs. OSF facilitates research producers/data administrators' creation of custom data use guidelines for sensitive/protected data that is only available through the "request access" mechanism.

OSF also has a dedicated data archiving or registering workflow, which preserves their content on OSF and a backup on Internet Archive. Users can associate funders with their OSF content using a built in Crossref Funder Registry API lookup so that the funder is identified reliably, as well as a resource type. When DOIs are minted for their data, the Funder ID is included. The user can also include a grant identifier, award title, or a URL associated with the award. They can also add DOIs connecting to their other study outputs, institutional affiliations, their personal ORCID iDs, and links to their related research outputs (materials, code, preregistrations, etc).

An OSF preregistration can leverage identifiers for people, resource outputs, research institutions, and funders in addition to resource type and discipline

GREI Use Cases are supported by the National Institutes of Health (NIH) Office of Data Science Strategy/ Office of the NIH Director pursuant to OTA-21-009, "Generalist Repository Ecosystem Initiative (GREI)". NIH Image Gallery. GDF10 protein forms new brain cell connections (<https://www.flickr.com/photos/nihgov/22798807131/>). Courtesy of S. Thomas Carmichael, MD, PhD, David Geffen School of Medicine at the University of California Los Angeles. NIH funding: National Institute of Neurological Disorders and Stroke (NINDS). More information at <https://www.nih.gov/news-events/news-releases/scientists-identify-main-component-brain-repair-after-stroke>

As a researcher, I want to **FIND** research data of interest in OSF so that I can validate findings, reuse data, and build on work within my discipline.

This use case highlights ways researchers can leverage generalist repositories to find datasets for reuse.

Dataset Title:

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Investigators and affiliations:

Brian Nosek
Center for Open Science & University of Virginia

Eric Olson
George Mason University

Date:

01/01/2023

Data type:

Survey results

Use Case Date:

04/24/2023

Use case Contact:

eric@cos.io

Background:

OSF is free to use by research producers and consumers. Research producers have fine control on privacy and security enabling them to keep some components of projects private and make other components publicly accessible. Research discovery is enhanced by robust metadata available on all content types, and an industry-exceeding search engine enables researchers to find precisely the data that they need.

Researchers can filter content by funder, institutional affiliations, resource type, license type, and relationships to preregistrations, papers, or additional data. They can then bookmark this content if they are an OSF user, or access and download all of the included files.

OSF also has a dedicated data archiving or registering workflow, where they can signal data reuse and replication through Open Science Badges. They can also add DOIs connecting to their institutional affiliations, their personal ORCID iDs, and links to their related research outputs (materials, code, preregistrations, etc).

The screenshot shows the OSF search interface with 6,755,825 results. On the left, there are several filter menus: Refine, Date Created, Funder, Subject, License, Resource Type, Collection, Institution, and Registry. On the right, there are two search results displayed. The first is a PROJECT titled "Adults' perspectives on young children's use of digital review of questionnaires used and findings" by Charlotte Lund Rasmussen, Amber Beynon, Sarah Stearne, and 10 more. The second is a REGISTRATION titled "Replication of Anger Damns the Innocent at BYU-I Wi" by Kayla Havens, Emma Jones, Kelsey O'Neal, and 2 more. Below the screenshot, a caption reads: "Researchers can use one or all of the many facets available in OSF Search to discover the data that they need."

As an institution, I want to **REPORT** on all datasets from my institution in OSF, so that I can ensure compliance of research data sharing and management plan commitments by our researchers.

This use case highlights ways administrators can leverage generalist repositories to track and report data sharing at an organizational level.

Dataset Title:

Data for: Effect of Preregistration on Reproducibility

Investigators and affiliations:

Brian Nosek
Center for Open Science & University of Virginia

Eric Olson
George Mason University

Date:

01/01/2023

Data type:

Survey results

Use Case Date:

01/01/2023

Use case Contact:

Gretchen@cos.io

Background:

To prevent misrepresentation and ensure consistent institutional reporting, OSF verifies affiliations for users from [institutional member organizations](#) through single sign-on with their institutional credentials or with their ORCID iDs. Once verified, institutional affiliations are added to users' profiles and can be added to their content.

A user can have multiple affiliations, and content can have affiliations from several contributors. If the institution has a Research Organization Identifier (ROR ID), this is also associated with the institution and its affiliated content. When DOIs are minted for affiliated content, the ROR IDs are included in the metadata provided. Affiliated users can also add resource types, funder information, and links to their related research outputs (materials, code, preregistrations, etc).

Institutional administrators can discover content from their community in several ways. All institutional members have a branded discovery page, which displays all of the public content affiliated with their institution as well as information about their organizational priorities and policies. Searching on OSF also enables multiple facets, so material can be filtered according to multiple factors. A user from an institution could use them to search only for datasets affiliated with a specific institution. They can limit the search even further to find only those associated with specific funder support. Content from OSF with DOIs are also shared through the Datacite or Crossref APIs with the institution's ROR ID, making it easy for them to query these sources or collect them in a CRIS system.

A public discovery page for affiliated content on OSF.

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As a funder from a specific NIH institute or in general, I want to find datasets we have funded in OSF, so that I can **REPORT** on compliance with policies, and **TRACK** impact of research funding and usage of data.

This use case highlights ways funders can leverage generalist repositories to track compliance with data sharing policies and understand data reuse.

Dataset Title:

Data for: Effect of Preregistration on Reproducibility

Investigators and affiliations:

Brian Nosek
Center for Open Science & University of Virginia

Eric Olson
George Mason University

Date:
01/01/2023

Data type:
Survey results

Use Case Date:
01/01/2023

Use case Contact:
Mark@cos.io

Background:

OSF enables robust metadata so that researchers can effectively identify themselves, their affiliations, their content, and their funders in a human and machine readable format.

Users can associate funders with their OSF content using a built in Crossref Funder Registry API lookup so that the funder is identified reliably. When DOIs are minted for their content, the Funder ID is included. The user can also include a grant identifier, award title, or a URL associated with the award. They can also add resource types, institutional affiliations, their personal ORCID iDs, and links to their related research outputs (materials, code, preregistrations, etc).

Funder program officers can discover content from their fundees in several ways. Searching on OSF enables multiple facets, so they can search for only dataset content that has indicated support from a specific funder. Because the funders are indicated by using the Crossref Funder Registry, there are no typos or alternative expressions of the funder's name to complicate a search. The Datacite API can also be queried with the funder's identifier, or the grant tracking systems can easily collect this information by discovering the related identifiers.

An OSF preregistration can leverage identifiers for people, resource outputs, research institutions, and funders in addition to resource type and discipline

GREI Use Cases are supported by the National Institutes of Health (NIH) Office of Data Science Strategy/ Office of the NIH Director pursuant to OTA-21-009, "Generalist Repository Ecosystem Initiative (GREI)". NIH Image Gallery. 3D image of actin in a cell (<https://www.flickr.com/photos/nihgov/33340166740/>). Credit: Credit: Xiaowei Zhuang, HHMI, Harvard University, and Nature Publishing Group. NIH support from: National Institute of General Medical Sciences (NIGMS)

As an institution, I want to capture and preserve lifecycle research materials from my institutional contributors by using OSF along with other institutional repositories.

This use case highlights ways generalist repositories support data sharing via institutional data repository infrastructure and workflows

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Data for: Effect of Preregistration on Reproducibility

Investigators and affiliations:

Brian Nosek
Center for Open Science & University of Virginia

Eric Olson
George Mason University

Date:

01/01/2024

Data type:

Survey results

Use Case Date:

05/14/2024

Use case Contact:

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Background:

As an institution, I want to complement our repository services by incorporating OSF membership for content my research community shares which might not be appropriate for our local repository on the OSF platform. I can capture and preserve research lifecycle data, reports, code, and other materials contributed to OSF that my own repository cannot manage. In addition, OSF allows my researchers to share and organize all the parts of their research process from an initial project registration, protocols and data created during analysis, and final dissemination through preprints. Any data format or file type can be stored and shared via OSF. My researchers can comply with funder data sharing requirements while keeping their content affiliated with institutional resources.

Because my institution is an OSF member, all content created by my community contains our institution's ROR identifier, and display our institution name and branding on the platform. Content from all of our research community is aggregated in a single searchable/filterable page in OSF. In addition, metadata from all of my researcher's OSF content is shared via an API with ROR identifiers making the data easy to harvest for downstream uses like current research information systems (CRIS) or ingestion into a local discovery environment. Through dashboards, reports and other tools I can track aggregate analytics, trends, and open practice adoption relative to peer institutions.

The image shows two screenshots from the OSF platform. The left screenshot is the 'OSF INSTITUTIONS' discovery page, featuring a search bar, a '1350 results' count, and a 'Refine' sidebar with filters for Creator, Date created, Funder, License, Resource type, Institution, Is part of collection, Includes community schema, and Has related resource. The right screenshot is the 'Content Page' for a project titled 'Replicability, Robustness, and Reproducibility in Psychological Science'. It displays project details such as contributors (Brian A. Nosek, Tom E. Hardwicke, Hannah Moshontz, Aurélien Allard, Katherine S. Corker, Anna Dreber Almenberg, Fiona Fidler, Joseph Hilgard, Melissa Kline Struhl, Michèle B. Nuijten, Julia M. Rohrer, Felipe Romero, Anne M. Scheel, Laura Scherer, Felix Schönbrodt, Simine Vazire), affiliated institutions (University of Virginia, Center For Open Science), date created (2020-06-11), last updated (2022-01-15), category (Project), description (Review for the Annual Review of Psychology, 2022), license (CC-BY Attribution 4.0 International), and a 'Wiki' section with a citation and components list.

OSF Institution Discovery Page and Content Page

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As a project consisting of hundreds of researchers, we want to collaboratively **USE OSF** to share **Big Data** whose volume, variety, velocity, or veracity requires special infrastructure functionality or handling

This use case highlights ways OSF supports Big Data via specialized functionality for large and complex dataset

Dataset Title:

Silent-Cities

Investigators and affiliations:

There are 261 contributors at 317 data collection sites distributed in 35 countries

DOI:

10.17605/OSF.IO/H285U

Data type:

Several audio formats, analysis scripts, package metadata, narrative support

Use case Contact:

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Background:

The **Silent Cities** initiative collected **large-scale** acoustic recordings during worldwide COVID-19 lockdowns. 261 contributors across 35 countries captured **high-resolution audio data**—often in real time—to measure shifts in urban soundscapes. To make this **4TB+** dataset openly accessible, easily understandable, and ready for interdisciplinary collaboration, our team leveraged **OSF** as a centralized, researcher curated repository.

Volume Challenge: Storing and sharing terabytes of raw audio recordings, spectrogram images, metadata files, and analysis scripts.

- *Large Storage Paid Services:* The team of hundreds of researchers purchased extended storage, accommodating far more than the standard 50GB limit.
- *Modular Project Structure:* Large audio data are separated into logical components (e.g., “Raw Audio,” “Processed Data,” “Documentation”), reducing confusion and download sizes for individual users.

Variety Challenge: Handling heterogeneous file formats, including WAV, FLAC, CSV metadata, analysis scripts (Python, R), and visual files (e.g., PNG spectrograms).

- *Flexible File-Type Support:* OSF accepts virtually any file format, ensuring that domain-specific data (like high-fidelity acoustic recordings) can be hosted (and most rendered) alongside more traditional text or code files.
- *Unified Metadata & README:* The team maintains thorough documentation for each file type to promote reusability and clarity.

Velocity Challenge: Data were generated and transferred at high speed, especially when capturing 24-hour audio streams from multiple cities simultaneously.

- *Scalable Upload Processes:* OSF’s command-line tools support batch uploads, allowing large datasets to flow in swiftly from different sites.
- *Immediate Collaboration:* Project contributors utilized third party storage integrations to allow contributors to quickly sync files, and then move to OSF Storage for long term preservation.

Veracity Challenge: Ensuring data quality and reliability (e.g., verifying correct timestamps, accurate calibrations, consistent sampling rates) across geographically dispersed teams and instruments.

- *Curation & Peer Review:* A dedicated curator and domain experts review dataset organization, file integrity, and metadata completeness, improving data accuracy and consistency. The project was also added to an OSF Collection featuring other quality COVID studies.
- *Version Control & Transparency:* OSF automatically tracks any file changes. If new data, corrected annotations, or updated scripts are uploaded, version history keeps the research record honest and reproducible.

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